

Practices of human resource management strategies and their role in achieving strategic flexibility in organizations

Al-Mafrachi Mustafa Saad & Hanaa Najm

Abstract

This study aimed to know the impact of human resource management strategies practices in enhancing strategic flexibility in organizations, and the study started from a number of hypotheses, which are: There is an effect of the practices of human resource management strategies in enhancing strategic flexibility in organizations, there is an impact of the practices of human resource management strategies in its dimensions (recruitment and selection Training and development) in enhancing the flexibility of the organizations 'expansion in the markets, and there is an impact of the practices of human resource management strategies in its dimensions (attracting and selecting - training and development) in enhancing the flexibility to provide new services and products in the markets. There is a positive relationship between the efficiency and effectiveness of selection and appointment strategies in organizations and their institutional performance, and there is also a positive relationship between the efficiency and effectiveness of strategies for evaluating the performance of workers in organizations and their institutional performance, according to the report.

Keywords: *Human Resources Management, Human Resources Strategies, Strategies Management, Strategic Flexibility.*

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Literature review

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1. Introduction:

The human element in the organization is considered one of the most important assets that the organization possesses. The human element is the one who invents, innovates, adds, renews, organizes, organizes and executes, and unless the organization has an effective human element, it will definitely suffer from a lack of competence and outstanding performance (Burkhardt et al., 2019). The human component, with its ability for advancement, inventiveness, creation, advancement and improvement, can beat the shortage of regular assets and not make them an obstruction to development. Progress through the better - if not ideal - abuse of the logical and gainful limits of society, just as the judicious misuse of characteristic assets and accessible ventures (Al-Husban, 2020). As a result of the current developments in the organizational environment of the organizations, this has necessitated the organizations to be concerned with adapting to them, as well as enhancing the flexibility of their production processes with the various services they provide. The product, the flexibility of the market in which this product is offered, as well as the flexibility related to the needs of customers in the market to reach a state of innovating new products that were not previously present in the market and in a way that meets the needs of customers and brings organizations to a degree of excellence in their processes and products (Rafael et al., 2019). On the other hand, the cognitive and technological factors have a great impact on work in organizations and the practices of human resources working in these organizations, and the level of human resources performance and the quality of organizations 'management are greatly affected by the elements prevailing in the organizational and administrative environment, and the behavior and performance of human resources inside and outside those organizations It is a reflection of the elements of the administrative and organizational environment, and accordingly, the market system and its components play a fundamental role in the life of organizations and human resources, but this effect of market factors and their dimensions necessarily differs according to the nature of those organizations and different human resources. There are additional interior variables identified with the idea of action and the field in which every association works, just as the level and example of the board and authority of this association and the nature of the HR working in it. Those variables make the associations that work in one industry contrast among themselves, and this distinction isn't just in the degree of execution or the degree of business results, yet additionally in the idea of the elements that structure the inward climate of the association influenced by the outer climate, which makes it extraordinary (Davidson et al., 2019). Figure No. (1), Shows the example of correspondence between HR the board and key execution through a model that reflects in detail the connection between business procedures and authoritative execution that is estimated by monetary markers. This model comprises execution as an element of capacity + inspiration + opportunity. It additionally shows that building up a system of Human assets comes in the wake of setting up a business technique (David and Collings, 2018). There are additionally interior variables identified with the idea of action and the field in which every association works, just as the level and example of the board and authority of this association and the nature of the HR working in it. Those variables make the associations that work in one industry contrast among themselves, and this distinction isn't just in the degree of execution or the degree of business results, yet additionally in the idea of the elements that structure the inward climate of the association influenced by the outer climate, which makes it extraordinary.

1.1 The problem of the study:

HR in associations address one of their most significant assets and perhaps the main resources that they have as it is absurd to expect to accomplish the objectives of these associations without the HR that associations should endeavor to focus on to have the option to accomplish their objectives, and because of extraordinary rivalry between associations in the business

sectors and the need to meet the cravings Customers, the matter calls for improving new items, venturing into different business sectors and offering various types of assistance. Thusly, the principle issue of this examination rotates around: What is the effect of human asset the board techniques rehearses in improving vital adaptability in associations?

This study paper helps to achieve the following objectives: (i) Knowing the impact of human resource management strategies practices in enhancing strategic flexibility in organizations & (ii). Make suggestions dependent on the consequences of the investigation that would upgrade human asset the board rehearses in the associations' essential adaptability.

1.2 Terminology of study:

1.2.1 Human resource management strategies:

It is the management of human resources activities related to recruitment and selection, training and development, maintaining the survival and sustainability of workers in the organization, caring for workers with unique competencies and specializations, providing equal job opportunities for all, building a climate of harmony among workers, and providing workers with the opportunity to recreate themselves (Sarah et al.,2013)

1.2.2 Strategic flexibility:

It is the capacity of associations to adjust to all types of changes that happen in the general climate by distributing assets and redistributing them to improve the focused-on presentation by recognizing the factors in the interior and outer climate to prepare assets towards new patterns and quick reactions to these progressions such that serves the necessities of clients and the desires and objectives of the associations (John et al., 2007).

The link between HRM and firm performance

Figure 1. The relationship between strategic HRM and performance. Source: Armstrong (2006, p. 75).

2 Literature review and the theoretical framework of the study:

2.1 Human resource management as a concept:

The term human resources has undergone a series of changes in terms of naming, content, and application associated with the designation, as this department began under the name of Manpower Department or Human Resources Department, and it is specialized in selecting, appointing, training, and developing workers in the organization (Fallon, L et al., 2013). It is noted from this concept that human resources management is nothing but activities or jobs that start with workers from their entry into the organization, and its role revolves around organizing the work of human resources with the organization more than it is a department concerned with investing human aspects in workers, and this is the functional entrance to the concept of management Modern human resources (Tapomoy et al., 2009). With the scientific development of management sciences in general, and the more attention paid to the human element in particular, human resources are seen as one of the most important assets in organizations, and therefore the role of human resource management is no longer limited to

functional administrative roles, but extended further than that to roles. Others, in response to environmental variables affecting the human resource, such as legal, social and economic variables (Kirk 2011).

2.2 HR Strategies Practices:

Human resource strategy practices focus on the following elements:

2.2.1 Polarization:

The cutting edge systems of the enlistment cycle depend on pulling in human components with different gifts, abilities, capacities and abilities and looking over among the best among them. It is additionally founded on incorporating qualified individuals inside a coordinated aggregate system, so the cutting edge work strategy is right now dependent on cooperation through work groups and not individual work. Which used to win in the past where the suitable individual was chosen, paying little heed to his gifts, capacities, and abilities to do a fixed work or work that keeps on performing as per what has been resolved for a long time without change or improvement to stay up with the quick changes in the inner and outer climate (Stephen et al., 2013). The process of recruiting and selecting employees is defined as the process that is concerned with searching for the appropriate human resources and attracting them from among the qualified and candidate human resources to fill vacant jobs in order to enable the selection process (K Aswathappa 2005).

2.2.2 Human resource selection:

What is meant by selecting human resources is the selection of employees, in the sense of selecting the human resources who have the required qualifications to accomplish certain or specific jobs as required, through a series of procedures or steps that begin with submitting a request for employment by the individual who wishes to hire and ends with the completion of the decision approving the selection One employee for each vacancy in the concerned organization (Donald et al., 2008). Although all organizations carry out the employee selection process within the human resource management activity, the similarity factor of this process varies from one organization to another (Adam et al., 2016).

2.2.3 Training and development:

Preparing and HR advancement happens in associations to attempt to give these assets the data, aptitude and abilities important to play out their work adequately. It is demonstrated that preparation and advancement has a few benefits, including expanding efficiency, raising the spirit of HR and diminishing the requirement for close management over them, as well as lessening work mishaps and developing particular information And upgrading the solidness and adaptability of the association (Krishnaveni, 2008). Despite the diversity and multiplicity of concepts and definitions of training, in the end they all refer to specific and clear meanings. Training is primarily concerned with providing human resources with specific skills and special knowledge whose primary role is to improve performance (Shaun, 2014). It ought to likewise be noticed that preparation is an arranged action that intends to achieve changes in the individual or gathering in all perspectives, like the data viewpoint, encounters, abilities, execution rates and work techniques, which makes the individual or gathering arrive at the fitting state to do the undertakings allotted to them (United, 2005).

2.2.4 Maintaining human resources:

Among the tasks of human resources management in the organization is to preserve these resources, and until this is achieved they must be developed in a sustainable way to reach institutional innovation, and this is done in several ways, including qualification that occurs through: training within clear plans, scholarships to complete studies, participation in conferences and seminars, Participating in committees and working groups, and providing references and periodicals (Torres, 2007). The human resources of the organization are also preserved through recognition, which includes: creating awards and rewards, measuring employee satisfaction, creating a system for evaluating subordinates to their superiors,

creating a system for complaints and suggestions, and creating a system of incentives linked to performance evaluation.

2.3 Strategic flexibility:

The term adaptability in everyday alludes to the capacity of the control framework in the association to screen the progressions that happen in the workplace in all regards and adjust to it, or it might mean the capacity of the association to change or react to hazards with low returns on schedule, exertion, cost, or execution, and that Flexibility is an unmistakable element of the association, through which it shows its capacity to interface between the elements of its authoritative climate and its outside climate(Wang et al.,2006).

2.4 Concept of strategic flexibility:

The accomplishment of associations in the contemporary workplace relies upon their capacity to adjust to changing economic situations. Albeit most worldwide associations receive new practices, for example, rebuilding, re-designing, complete quality administration and convenient conveyance to stay inside the structure of rivalry, these practices are not adequate, as they contribute In ceaseless improvement just and doesn't attempt to create a maintainable upper hand, as the consideration should be coordinated towards key adaptability since it upholds the advancement of future systems as it empowers the association to adjust and react rapidly to the changing idea of the inward and outer climate factors (Sushil, 2013). The idea of vital adaptability incorporates the capacity of associations to react rapidly to promising circumstances and ecological changes. Subsequently, associations should acknowledge key adaptability because of the significance of accomplishing another upper hand for a few reasons, including: that essential adaptability is a condition for expanding the associations 'capacity to confront significant and quick natural changes that cause fast change in business sectors. Managing it requires high productivity and adequacy, and the essential adaptability empowers the association in these conditions to deal with its exercises (Torben, 2019). Notwithstanding the abovementioned, vital adaptability upgrades the capacity of associations and their capacity to react to changing client needs and wants and to uncover client inclinations through the association's communication with its clients (Abou-Zeid, 2007). Strategic flexibility also increases the organizations' ability to display their products in multiple markets, which leads to generating added value that helps the growth and survival of these organizations (Michele, 2012).

2.5 The importance of strategic flexibility:

The importance of strategic flexibility stems from the fact that it enables the organization to change its strategy and adapt to market trends, thereby making it capable of rapidly responding to environmental opportunities and changes. The organization's work with strategic flexibility also leads to the development of its capacity in creating new products, entering new markets, and not only structuring its size and product volume according to changing market requirements (Michele, 2012). Likewise, the organization's dealing with strategic flexibility reflects its ability to achieve competitiveness in changing competitive environments (Tony, 2005)

2.6 Dimensions and measures of strategic flexibility:

Strategic resilience consists of a number of implications that involve developing strategies commensurate with the realities of the environment in which you operate in terms of adaptation, adaptability, modification, flexibility, precaution, moderation, resilience, shock tolerance, resilient setback and shock tolerance (Tobias, 2009).

And the fact that strategic flexibility is of great importance to the success of business organizations, so it is natural that the focus on it by the top management of organizations is great, and improving the strategic flexibility of organizations is achieved by focusing on the following three basic dimensions (Eric, 2013):

2.6.1 Thinking: It as a rule adds to improving the capacity of associations to roll out the necessary improvements before different associations, and that reasoning requires doing natural investigation and creating options and inescapable situations to make the most of chances and upgrade the essential abilities of the association.

2.6.2 Role-playing skills: This measurement permits the association to infer more extensive dreams and initiate business by accentuating development and innovativeness, and if associations recognized in this measurement have the capacity to investigate the future in principle, at that point this component of pretend encapsulates reasonable abilities and experimentation with items and administrations, and accordingly Shaping, framing and building the ideal future.

2.6.3 Investment: It empowers the association to get forward and invert takes care of that help its essential choices, through the presence of a solid authoritative culture supported with right administrative structures.

2.7 The impact of human resource strategies practices and their role in achieving strategic flexibility in organizations:

According to the findings of several studies, there is a positive relationship between the efficiency and effectiveness of organizational selection and appointment strategies and their institutional performance, as well as a positive relationship between the efficiency and effectiveness of organizational strategies for evaluating worker performance and their institutional performance (Carolina 2014). With regard to the practices related to the organizations' training strategy and their impact on the level of human resources performance of their employees, there is a strong positive correlation between the degree of practice of human resource managers of the stages of the training process and the level of performance of the human resources working in them (Abou-Zeid, 2007).

Based on the above discussion, this study attempts to test the following hypotheses:

- **H1:** There is an effect of human asset the board methodologies rehearses in improving vital adaptability in associations.
- **H2:** There is an effect of the acts of human asset the executives systems in its measurements (polarization and determination - preparing and advancement) in improving the adaptability of the extension of associations in the business sectors.
- **H3:** There is an impact of the practices of human resource management strategies in its dimensions (recruitment and selection - training and development) in enhancing the flexibility of providing new services and products in the markets.

Conclusion:

The role of human resources management is no longer limited to functional administrative roles, but rather extended to other roles in response to environment variables affecting the human resource such as legal, social and economic variables. Additionally, modern strategies for the recruitment process are based on attracting human elements with multiple talents, skills, abilities and capabilities, and choosing from among the best among them. Also, training and advancement of HR happens in associations to attempt to furnish these assets with the data, mastery and abilities important to play out their work adequately. It is shown that preparation and improvement have a few benefits, including expanding efficiency, raising the resolve of HR and decreasing the requirement for close oversight. Among the tasks of human resources management in the organization is to preserve these resources, and until this is achieved, they must be developed in a sustainable way to reach institutional innovation, and this is done in several ways, including qualification that occurs through: training within clear plans, scholarships to complete studies, participation in conferences and seminars, participating in committees and working groups, and providing references and periodicals.

The achievement of associations in the contemporary workplace relies upon their capacity to adjust to changing economic situations. Albeit most worldwide associations receive new practices, for example, rebuilding, re-designing, all out quality administration and ideal conveyance to stay inside the structure of rivalry, these practices are not adequate, as they contribute It is just in consistent improvement and doesn't produce reasonable upper hand.

The idea of vital adaptability incorporates the capacity of associations to react rapidly to promising circumstances and natural changes, so associations should acknowledge vital adaptability because of the significance of accomplishing another upper hand for a few reasons, including: that essential adaptability is a condition for expanding the associations 'capacity to confront significant and fast ecological changes that cause quick change in business sectors and require Dealing with high productivity and viability, and the essential adaptability empowers the association in these conditions to deal with its exercises. Moreover, strategic resilience consists of a number of implications that involve developing strategies commensurate with the realities of the environment in which you operate in terms of adaptability, adaptability, modification, flexibility, precaution, activation, resilience, shock tolerance, resilient setback and shock tolerance. Also, there is a positive connection between the productivity and adequacy of determination and arrangement systems in associations and their institutional exhibition, and there is additionally a positive connection between the proficiency and viability of techniques for assessing the presentation of laborers in associations and their institutional exhibition, notwithstanding that there is a positive connection between the productivity and viability of representative preparing methodologies in associations and their institutional exhibition. With respect to the practices identified with the associations' preparation procedure and their effect fair and square of HR execution of their representatives, there is a solid positive relationship between the level of training of human asset chiefs of the phases of the preparation cycle and the degree of execution of the HR working in them.

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